
Analysis of Patient Satisfaction in Health BPJS Services in Wilaya Garut Hospital, West Java- Indonesia

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ABSTRACT:

Background: Based on the result data release received on the official website of the Organizing Body Social Security on March 1, 2022 is available as many as 10,234 souls BPJS participants as user facility health the most that are (BPJS Health, 2022). Based on Perpres Number 12 of 2013 Article 21 states that, the First Level Health Facility (FKTP) is a service handling health stage beginning at the health center as the primary level in gift service health. In the Health Center JKN/BPJS system owns a sufficient role for all BPJS Health participants.

Methods; Study This is a study descriptive analytic qualitative with an approach *cross-sectional*. The sampling technique *purposive sampling* is a sampling technique with certain considerations.

Results; Education Variables with a *p*- *p*-value of 0.383 which means No There is no significant relationship and variables Type sex with an value *p-value* of 0.043 which means There is a meaningful relationship between type sex on satisfaction Health BPJS services.

Conclusions; Conclusion from study This is an influential variable with Satisfaction patients with BPJS service is a type variable Sex.

KEYWORDS: Satisfaction, Service, Health BPJS

INTRODUCTION

Health is the right basic man and one element necessary welfare _ embodied in accordance with the ambition of the Indonesian nation as meant in Pancasila and the 1945 Constitution of the Republic of Indonesia (RI Law No. 36 of 2009). Health is important and much needed _ for every human. Increasing social status in society, p this too can influence provider service health to be more increase the quality in giving service (Rahmawati Dewi, 2016). Article 28 H paragraph (1) of the 1945 Constitution states that “everyone has the right life prosperous physically and mentally, place stay and earn environment good and healthy life _ as well as entitled obtain service health”. Furthermore, Article 34 paragraph (3) is affirmed that “the State is responsible for providing facility service health and facilities service decent public”. The Indonesian government still Keeps trying to achieve UHC (Universal Health Coverage) or as it is known with scope health universe. With the achievement of UHC, the public can own access to fulfilling need service health-promotive, preventive, curative, and rehabilitative with quality and effective services (Puspa, 2020). In realizing UHC, the first Health BPJS operated on January 1, 2014, which was transformed from PT Askes (Persero). Starting in 2004 when the government Law No. 40 established a law on System National Social Security (SJSN), namely Law Number 24 of 2011 concerning the Administrative Body Social Security in the Health Sector, PT Askes (Persero) became BPJS Health (BPJS Health, 2021). The total number of JKN-KIS program participants as of October 1, 2021, is recorded as many as 226,360,454 people. JKN-KIS participants have six class type participation, among others ie Recipient Help Dues -APBN (PBI-APBN) totaling 95,067,648 people, Recipients Help Contributions -APBD (PBI-APBD) of 36,923,400 people, workers Recipient Civil Servant Wages (PPU-PN) totaling 18,293,774, Workers Recipient Wages for Business Entities (PPU-BU) totaling 40,636,697 people, Workers No Recipient Wage (PBPU)- Workers Independent several 31,065,038 souls, no Workers (BP) totaling 4,373,897 people (BPJS Health, 2021). According to Updating results of the JKN-KIS Program Deputy for the West Java Region in 2020, there are 46,092,205 people who have registered to become BPJS participants. with 6 groups participation, among others Recipient Help Contributions - APBN (APBN PBI) totaling 16,773,465 people, workers Recipient Wages (PPU) of 10,686,336 people, workers No Recipient Wages (PBPU) of 6,515,871 people, Recipients Help Dues -APBD (PBI-APBD) totaling 4,430,702 people, No Workers (BP) totaling 779,712 people (BPJS Health, 2020). Based on yield data released by the official website of the Organizing Body Social

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Security on March 1, 2022, is available as many as 10,234 souls BPJS participants used facility health in most Public health centers (BPJS Health, 2022). Based on Perpres Number 12 of 2013 Article 21 states that, the First Level Health Facility (FKTP) is a service handling health stage beginning at the health center as the primary level in gift service health. In the Health Center JKN/BPJS system owns a sufficient role for all BPJS Health participants.

METHODS

Study This is study descriptive analytic qualitative with a approach *cross-sectional*. In studying this, the researcher wants to know the connection between variable Characteristics of the individual (Type sex, and Education) and the Satisfaction of patients with BPJS services. The population contained in the study is that whole patient BPJS Kesehatan participants are good to head family and accompanying start from 17 years old and still active as BPJS Health participants. The sampling technique purposive *sampling* is a sampling technique with certain considerations (Sugiyono, 2003: 78). Big sample was obtained in the study of 131 respondents. In research this is the instrument used is questionnaire satisfaction services at the Health Center Cimareme about expectations and reality received by the patient are compiled with question closed, on the question This respondent stay choose considered answer Correct Because choice answer Already provided by researchers.

RESULT

Figure 1: Characteristics of Respondents Based on Education
Source: Primary Data, 2022

Figure 1 explains partly big dominating respondents are 35.9 % of respondents with a Senior High School education distribution frequency respondent of 108 respondents and the fewest respondents are respondents with a Junior High School education percentage of 14.6% with distribution respondents answered 44 respondents

Figure 2: Characteristics Respondents Based on Type Sex
Source: Primary Data, 2022

Figure 2 explains the distribution Type Sex respondent, where types of respondents sex Woman own percentage by 62% and the type of respondents sex man percentage by 38%

Figure 3: Respondent Data Based on Satisfaction
Source: Primary Data, 2022

Figure 3 shows the percentage of satisfaction among Respondents to BPJS Health services, Most respondents stated Satisfied with BPJS Health services with a percentage 58% distribution respondent of 176 respondents, and respondents who were not satisfied 42%.

Table 1. Relationship Satisfaction Patient on satisfaction Health BPJS services

Satisfaction		Satisfied		No Satisfied		Total	P-value	Or (95% CI)
Characteristics		n	%	n	%	n		
Education								
Elementary School		61	61	39	39	100	100	0.383
Junior High School		21	46.7	24	53.3	45	100	
High School		63	60	42	40	105	100	
College		31	60.8	20	39.2	51	100	
Type Sex								
male		62	54.9	51	45.1	113	100	0.043
female		114	60.6	74	39.4	188	100	

Source: Primary Data, 2022

Based on Table 1, results show that most respondents who answered satisfied with BPJS Kesehatan services respondents who have a High School Education with percentage of 60% with amount respondent by 63 respondents of 105 respondents with a high school education. With a *p*-value of 0.383 it means No There is a significant relationship. The type of respondents with female genitals answered Satisfied with BPJS Health services with a percentage of 60.6%, with mark *p-values* of 0.043 which means There is a meaningful relationship between type sex on satisfaction with Health BPJS services.

DISCUSSION

Education Relations with Satisfaction BPJS patients

Based on variable study data obtained from 301 respondents obtained results respondents who had more high school education Lots ie of 105 respondents or 35.9%, compared to educated respondents scholar 51 respondents or 16.9% educated respondents College. Education is a learning process and a process of growth and development to be more directionwell, mature, and riper. The more education somebody so the easier it is to accept the information he got. Otherwise, if somebody’s level of education is low, got hinders the development of somebody in accepting new information and values introduced. learning process No will happen so just if No accompanies something that helps the person concerned (Soekanto, 2011). As for the levels of education in Indonesia as listed in Law No. 20 of 2003 concerning system education divided national for 3 formal education namely Basic Education (DS/madrasah ibtidaiyah /SMP/ MTsn), Secondary Education (SMU/madrasah aliyah and equivalent), and Higher Education (Academic / University high) (Secretary of State of the Republic of Indonesia, 2003). If seen from the condition in the field, by general part big level more education dominant is high school graduates and some small is college high. Education taken somebody is a process of change Act do, more and more tall education so the more Lots knowledge as well as information about known health. The more tall education, makes it easier is for somebody to accept information. With higher education, someone will tend to get good information from other people around him or from the mass media. The more Lots information obtained, the more Lots acquired knowledge,

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including knowledge about health. this is in line with research conducted by Susilo (2018) which shows the result is $p=0.007$ which means No There is a connection between education with satisfaction among patients.

Connection Type sex with BPJS patients

Respondents on research This is patient BPJS Health participants only. Amount respondents who are researchers compared amounted to 301 respondents based on type sex show that respondent Women were the most dominant, that is as many as 188 respondents (62%) meanwhile respondent man as many as 113 respondents (38%). Viewed from the data (Kotler, 2006). In accordance with conditions on the ground show that part big very satisfied patients is with type sex girls. this is because there is a difference in properties secondary, emotionality, and activity in women and men so Women more dominant use feeling to evaluate ability or conditions in service health, different from men more man dominant use logic to evaluate something. According to Suryati (2017), that type of sex has a significant influence on views of services provided more women Lots see an appearance in detail, meanwhile, men Do to notice matter. The study, This Woman More Lots highlights the reliability of officer health in giving service, especially for BPJS participants. Owned reliability officer health is a quality service that can used as a stepping stone so that the services provided can satisfy the user in matter patient. Reliability Officer health This self from officer health gives action nursing in a manner correct and appropriate with set - set Standard Operational Procedures (SOP), officers also always give action treatment at the appropriate time, information action treatment given easily understandable and appropriate with patient complaints, officers always notice health and safety patient, as well in give service No enforce discrimination or discriminate patient BPJS. The same thing with research conducted by Herliana (2017) the result is a p -value of 0.003 in other words there is a significant relationship between the type of sex with satisfied patients. The same thing with research conducted by Silprihatin (2017) with the result $p = 0.032$ which means that the type of sex with satisfaction patient relationship is significant.

CONCLUSION

The conclusion from the study This is an influential variable with Satisfaction among patients with BPJS service is a type variable Sex mark p -values of 0.043 while the variable is not influential is Education.

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